

The Street as Place, A Place for Mobility: Investigating the Spatial Allocation of Transport Infrastructure

Extended abstract of the COSIT 2024 doctoral mentorship program

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The street has come into focus as the arena of change in cities today. Academic, political, and popular movements converge on changing the streetscape to better meet people's needs, and much of this momentum is around mobility, and transport infrastructure in particular. A growing critique looks at the extent to which automobiles dominate the mobility landscape [10], in terms of the space they occupy on the roadway [2], how they have transformed streets from places in which to exist, to roadways to move through [13], their greenhouse gas emissions [14], and the injuries and fatalities caused by collisions [17]. Today, many cities are undergoing an "urban mobility transition" [12] away from the domineering "system of automobility" [19], through an active process that involves the contention and negotiation of street space.

An emerging scholarship grounded in the critical discourses of mobility justice [16] and transport justice [9] investigates how street space is allocated to different transport modes through quantitative investigations of spatial allocation [8], as well as discussions of how street space could be reallocated to better suit contemporary visions of good, fair, and just cities [3]. This research project adds to this literature by investigating how street space is allocated to transport infrastructures, through the following guiding research questions:

- How can the allocation of street space to transport infrastructures, and the inequality of that allocation across space, be represented in spatial statistical measures, and what do these measures indicate about streets as places?
- How can the "human scale" concept apply to mobility on the street, and how can doing so inform considerations of street space re(allocation)?
- How does taking the street as the basic unit of analysis in investigations of mobility, inform the approaches and methods used in mobility research?

First, I will review methods of measuring and evaluating street space allocation from existing studies [1, 6] and replicate them to compare their utility, strengths, and weaknesses. This will support the emerging field of street space allocation studies by providing researchers with a guide for the use and development of relevant methods and tools.

Second, I will design a statistical measure to capture the inequality in the space allocated on the street between the infrastructure of transport modes. Using road asset and travel survey data from several Canadian cities, this study will measure the space allocated to infrastructure per travel mode, explore how this relates to the number of travellers using that mode, and develop a measure that intuitively captures any inequality in the space provided per traveller, by mode. This study also will consider how this measure of inequality is related to the socioeconomic characteristics of the population, across cities.

Third, I will construct a theoretical framework around the interaction between place, mobility, and scale towards generating guiding principles for street space (re)allocation. This work is grounded in the concept of "human scale" from design and architecture literature [4, 11], and will adapt it to the study of mobility, while also drawing from theoretical work in geographical information science on the nature of place [18, 15, 7] and scale [5]. The developed theoretical framework will support exploring how street space allocation may be

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guided by the principle of matching the mobility landscape to the experience of the “human scale”.

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